

An Order Level Inventory Model for Decaying Items with Trade Credits and Lost Sales

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Abstract

This paper deals with an order level inventory model with quadratic demand. The effect of deterioration is a very natural incident therefore variable deterioration rate is taken into account. Shortages are allowed in inventory with partial backlogging. Backlogging rate is taken as exponential decreasing function of time. Numerical examples are also used to study the behavior of the model.

Keywords: Inventory, Shortages, Variable deterioration, Quadratic demand, Partial Backlogging.

Introduction

In some cases such as retailer, wholesaler/distributor, where items are purchased externally, if the problem of inventory exists, then there are two main questions, which generally arise and face any organization. These are how many to order and when to order. Having too much inventory reduces both purchase and /or ordering costs, but it may tie up capital, which may lead to unnecessary holding cost and possibility of deteriorating items. Whereas having too little inventory reduces the holding cost, but it can result in lost of customers, which may affect the reliability of the organization. Answering these two questions will lead to the optimal level of inventory for any organization, which minimizes its total inventory cost. If an item required by a customer is not currently available in the organization stores, then the customer either goes to another place (a lost customer), or alternatively, places a backorder for the item. Some organizations are either sole supplier, providing a competitive price, or offering a discount for delaying the delivery of certain items. If this is the case, an organization does not lose the sale when its inventory is depleted. Instead, the customer has to wait for his order to be filled whenever a new order

arrives. Therefore, backordering or shortages are the demand that will be filled some time later than desired.

Many researchers considered the constant demand rates in their inventory models, but the assumptions of constant demand are not always applicable in real situations. The researchers have so far considered only two types of time-varying demands, namely, linear and exponential. A linearly time-varying demand implies a uniform change in the demand rate of the product per unit time. This is a fairly unrealistic phenomenon and it seldom occurs in the real market. In recent times, some researchers have worked with an exponentially time-varying demand. The demand for some items like spare parts of new aero-planes and other machines, new computer chips etc. increases rapidly while that for obsolete machine parts and computers decreases rapidly. Some modelers represented this type of demand as an exponentially increasing/decreasing function of time. An exponential rate of change is very high and it is doubtful whether the real market demand of any product undergoes a rate of change which is as high as an exponential rate is. An alternative (perhaps realistic) approach would be to consider a time-quadratic demand which may represent both accelerated and retarded growth in demand.

Dave [1] proposed a deterministic lot-size inventory model with shortages and a linear trend in demand. **Mandal and Phaujdar [2]** then developed a production inventory model for deteriorating items with uniform rate of production and linearly stock dependent demand. **Datta and Pal [3]** extended **Mandal and Phaujdar's** work for deteriorating items with assumption that demand rate is a linear function of the on-hand inventory by allowing shortages, which are completely backlogged for both finite and infinite time horizons. **Goswami and Chaudhuri [4]** discussed different types of inventory models with linear trend in demand. **Mandal and Maiti [5]** discussed an inventory of damageable items with variable replenishment rate and deterministic demand. **Gupta and Aggarwal [6]** discussed different types of inventory models with linear trend in demand. **Khanra and Chaudhuri [7]** discussed an order level decaying inventory model with such time dependent quadratic demand. **Dye [8]** developed a deteriorating inventory model with stock-dependent demand and partial backlogging. **Balkhi and Benkherouf [9]** developed an inventory model for deteriorating items with stock dependent and time varying demand rates over a finite planning horizon. **Wu et al. [10]** proposed an optimal replenishment policy for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with stock-dependent demand and partial backlogging. **Ouyang [11]** presented an inventory problem for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with stock dependent demand when supplier offers an all unit quantity discount. A mathematical was developed by **Soni and Shah [12]** to formulate optimal ordering policies for retailer when demand was partially constant and partially dependent on the stock.

Assumptions and Notations

To develop an inventory model with variable demand and partial backlogging the following notations and assumptions are used:

Assumptions

- Demand rate is taken as quadratic.
- Deterioration rate is time dependent.
- Shortages are allowed with partial backlogging.
- Backlogging rate is an exponential decreasing function of time.
- Replenishment rate is infinite.
- A single item is considered over the prescribed interval.
- There is no repair or replenishment of deteriorated units.

Notations

- $I(t)$ The inventory level at time t .
- θt Variable rate of defective units out of on hand inventory at time t , $0 < \theta \ll 1$.
- C' The inventory ordering cost per order.
- C_1 The holding cost per unit per unit time
- C_2 Unit purchase cost per unit
- C_3 Shortage cost per unit per unit time
- C_4 Lost sale cost per unit per unit time
- t_1 The time at which shortage starts and T is the length of replenishment cycle. $0 \leq t_1 \leq T$.

$f(t) = a + bt + ct^2$ The variable demand rate is, $a > 0$, $b > 0$, $c > 0$ and $a > b > c$.

Here a is initial rate of demand; b is the rate with which the demand rate increases. The rate of change in demand rate itself increases at a rate c .

$\text{Exp}(-\delta x)$ Unsatisfied demand is backlogged at a rate; the backlogging parameter δ is a positive constant.

Formulation and Solution of The Model

The depletion of inventory during the interval $(0, t_1)$ is due to joint effect of demand and deterioration of items and the demand is partially backlogged in the interval (t_1, T) .

The differential equations describing the inventory level $I(t)$ in the interval $(0, T)$ are given by

$$I'(t) + \theta t I(t) = -f(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \quad \dots(1)$$

$$I'(t) = -f(t) e^{-\delta t}, \quad t_1 \leq t \leq T \quad \dots(2)$$

With the conditions, $I(t_1) = 0$ and $I(0) = S$.

The solutions of equations (6.1) and (6.2) can be obtained as

$$I(t) = a(t_1 - t) + \frac{b}{2}(t_1^2 - t^2) + \frac{c}{3}(t_1^3 - t^3) + \frac{a\theta}{6}(t_1^3 - 3t_1t^2 + 2t^3) \\ + \frac{b\theta}{8}(t_1^2 - t^2)^2 + \frac{c\theta}{30}(3t_1^5 - 5t_1^3t^2 + 2t^5), \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\text{And } I(t) = \left\{ a\delta^2 + b\delta(\delta t + 1) + c(\delta^2 t^2 + 2\delta t + 2) \right\} \frac{e^{-\delta t}}{\delta^3} \\ - \left\{ a\delta^2 + b\delta(\delta t_1 + 1) + c(\delta^2 t_1^2 + 2\delta t_1 + 2) \right\} \frac{e^{-\delta t_1}}{\delta^3}, \quad t_1 \leq t \leq T \quad \dots(4)$$

Also the initial inventory level

$$S = at_1 + \frac{b}{2}t_1^2 + \left(c + \frac{a\theta}{2} \right) \frac{t_1^3}{3} + \frac{b\theta t_1^4}{8} + \frac{c\theta t_1^5}{10} \quad \dots(5)$$

The inventory holding cost (C_H) per cycle is given by

$$C_H = C_1 \int_0^{t_1} I(t) dt \\ = C_1 \left(\frac{at_1^2}{2} + \frac{bt_1^3}{3} + \frac{ct_1^4}{4} + \frac{a\theta t_1^4}{12} + \frac{b\theta t_1^5}{15} + \frac{c\theta t_1^6}{18} \right) \quad \dots(6)$$

The deterioration cost (C_D) per cycle is given by

$$C_D = C_2 \left\{ I(0) - \int_0^{t_1} f(t) dt \right\} \\ = C_2 \left\{ \frac{a\theta t_1^3}{6} + \frac{b\theta t_1^4}{8} + \frac{c\theta t_1^5}{10} \right\} \quad \dots(7)$$

The shortage cost (C_S) per cycle due to backlog is given by

$$C_S = -C_3 \int_{t_1}^T I(t) dt \\ = \frac{C_3}{\delta^4} \left\{ a\delta^2 + b\delta(2 + \delta T) + c(6 + 4\delta T + \delta^2 T^2) \right\} e^{-\delta T}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{C_3}{\delta^4} \left[a\delta^2 \{1 - \delta(T - t_1)\} + b\delta \{ (2 - \delta T)(1 + \delta t_1) + \delta^2 t_1^2 \} \right. \\
 & \left. + c \{ 6 + 6\delta t_1 + \delta^2 t_1^2 - 2\delta T - \delta^2 (T - t_1)(2t_1 + \delta t_1^2) \} \right] e^{-\delta t_1} \quad \dots(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

And the opportunity cost (C_0) per cycle due to lost sales is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_0 &= C_4 \int_{t_1}^T (1 - e^{-\delta t})(a + bt + ct^2) dt \\
 &= C_4 \left[a(T - t_1) + \frac{b}{2}(T^2 - t_1^2) + \frac{c}{3}(T^3 - t_1^3) + \frac{1}{\delta^3} \{ a\delta^2 + b\delta(1 + \delta T) \right. \\
 & \left. + c(2 + 2\delta T + \delta^2 T^2) \} e^{-\delta T} - \frac{1}{\delta^3} \{ a\delta^2 + b\delta(1 + \delta t_1) \right. \\
 & \left. + c(2 + 2\delta t_1 + \delta^2 t_1^2) \} e^{-\delta t_1} \right] \quad \dots(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the total average cost of the system is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 TC &= \frac{1}{T} (C' + C_H + C_D + C_S + C_O) \quad \dots(10) \\
 &= \frac{1}{T} \left[C' + C_1 \left(\frac{at_1^2}{2} + \frac{bt_1^3}{3} + \frac{ct_1^4}{4} + \frac{a\theta t_1^4}{12} + \frac{b\theta t_1^5}{15} + \frac{c\theta t_1^6}{18} \right) \right. \\
 & \left. + C_2 \left\{ \frac{a\theta t_1^3}{6} + \frac{b\theta t_1^4}{8} + \frac{c\theta t_1^5}{10} \right\} + \frac{C_3}{\delta^4} \{ a\delta^2 + b\delta(2 + \delta T) + c(6 + 4\delta T + \delta^2 T^2) \} e^{-\delta T} \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{C_3}{\delta^4} \left[a\delta^2 \{1 - \delta(T - t_1)\} + b\delta \{ (2 - \delta T)(1 + \delta t_1) + \delta^2 t_1^2 \} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + c \{ 6 + 6\delta t_1 + \delta^2 t_1^2 - 2\delta T - \delta^2 (T - t_1)(2t_1 + \delta t_1^2) \} \right] e^{-\delta t_1} \right. \\
 & \left. + C_4 \left[a(T - t_1) + \frac{b}{2}(T^2 - t_1^2) + \frac{c}{3}(T^3 - t_1^3) + \frac{1}{\delta^3} \{ a\delta^2 + b\delta(1 + \delta T) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + c(2 + 2\delta T + \delta^2 T^2) \} e^{-\delta T} - \frac{1}{\delta^3} \{ a\delta^2 + b\delta(1 + \delta t_1) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + c(2 + 2\delta t_1 + \delta^2 t_1^2) \} e^{-\delta t_1} \right] \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

To minimize total average cost per unit time, the optimal values of t_1 and T can be obtained by solving the following equations simultaneously

$$\frac{\partial TC}{\partial t_1} = 0 \quad \dots(11)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{\partial TC}{\partial T} = 0 \quad \dots(12)$$

provided they satisfy the following conditions

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial^2 TC}{\partial t_1^2} > 0, \frac{\partial^2 TC}{\partial T^2} > 0 \\ \text{and } \left(\frac{\partial^2 TC}{\partial t_1^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 TC}{\partial T^2} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial^2 TC}{\partial t_1 \partial T} \right)^2 > 0 \end{array} \right\} \quad \dots(13)$$

The numerical solution of these equations can be obtained by using some suitable computational numerical method.

Numerical Illustration

To illustrate the model numerically the following parameter values are considered.

$$\begin{array}{ll} a = 25 \text{ units,} & C' = \text{Rs.250 per order} \\ b = 12 \text{ units,} & C_1 = \text{Rs.2.0 per unit per year} \\ c = 5 \text{ units,} & C_2 = \text{Rs.12.0 per unit} \\ \theta = 0.04 \text{ units,} & C_3 = \text{Rs.15 per unit per year} \\ C_4 = \text{Rs. 3.0 per unit} & \end{array}$$

Then for the minimization of total average cost and with help of software

Matlab 7.0.1 the optimal policy can be obtained such as

$$t_1 = 0.89456, \quad T = 2.7834, \quad TC = 58.2408$$

Analytical Graph of Total Cost

When we plot the graph between the parameter a and t_1 then we find that increase in a increases t_1 .

Conclusion

In this paper we developed a lot size inventory model for a single deteriorated item with time dependent quadratic demand. Shortages are allowed and backlogging rate is dependent on the waiting time for the next replenishment. Here we discussed the effect of variation on total cost due to various parameters of the system and given analytical solution of the model that minimizes the total cost.

From the analysis of model, it has been concluded that if the demand parameters are increases then the time and total cost will also increase. If the deterioration parameter increases then the time will decrease and total cost will increase.

Table 1: Variation in system parameters

Parameter	%	-50	-25	0	25	50
a	t_1	0.89398	0.89441	0.89456	0.89463	0.89479
	T	2.7281	2.7646	2.7834	2.8067	2.8193
	TC	57.8903	58.1145	58.2408	58.8923	59.0632
b	t_1	0.89362	0.89435	0.89456	0.89489	0.89496
	T	2.7190	2.7578	2.7834	2.8124	2.8347
	TC	55.6719	56.7891	58.2408	59.6720	60.8914
c	t_1	0.82624	0.84495	0.89456	0.91672	0.93781
	T	2.7365	2.7645	2.7834	2.7964	2.8352
	TC	54.3672	55.7823	58.2408	60.4721	62.2574
θ	t_1	0.93789	0.91681	0.89456	0.85782	0.82163
	T	2.8289	2.7923	2.7834	2.7735	2.7379
	TC	53.6705	55.2289	58.2408	61.7820	63.8203

Figure 1: Variation in 'a' w.r.t. ' t_1 '

Figure 2: Variation in 'a' w.r.t. 'T'

Figure 3: Variation in 'a' w.r.t. total cost

Figure 4: Variation in 'b' w.r.t. ' t_1 '

Figure 5: Variation in 'b' w.r.t. 'T'

Figure 6: Variation in 'b' w.r.t. total cost

Figure 7: Variation in 'c' w.r.t. ' t_1 '

Figure 8: Variation in 'c' w.r.t. 'T'

Figure 9: Variation in 'c' w.r.t. total cost

Figure 10: Variation in 'theta' w.r.t. ' t_1 '

Figure 11: Variation in 'θ' w.r.t. 'T'

Figure 12: Variation in 'θ' w.r.t. total cost

References

- [1] U. Dave, On a heuristic inventory-replenishment rule for items with a linearly increasing demand incorporating shortages, *J O R S*, **38(5)**, (1989), 459-463.
- [2] B. N. Mandal and S. Phaujdar, An inventory model for deteriorating items and stock dependent consumption rate, *J O R S*, **40**, (1989), 483-488.
- [3] T. K. Datta and A. K. Pal, Deterministic inventory systems for deteriorating items with inventory level dependent demand and shortages, *J O R S*, **27**, (1990), 213-224.
- [4] A. Goswami and K. S. Chaudhuri, An EOQ model for deteriorating items with a linear trend in demand, *JORS*, **42(12)**, (1991), 1105-1110.
- [5] M. Mandal and M. Maiti, Inventory of damageable items with variable replenishment rate, stock-dependent demand and some units in hand, *App. Math. Modeling*, **23**, (1999), 799-807.
- [6] P. N. Gupta and R. N. Aggarwal, An order level inventory model with time dependent deterioration, *Opsearch*, **37(4)**, (2000) 351-359.

- [7] S. Khanra and K. S. Chaudhuri , A note on an order-level inventory model for a deteriorating item with time-dependent quadratic demand, *C.O.R.*, **30**, (2003), 1901-1916.
- [8] C. Y. Dye, A deteriorating inventory model with stock dependent demand and partial backlogging under conditions of permissible delay in payments, *Opsearch*, **39 (3 & 4)**, (2002), 189-200.
- [9] Z. T. Balkhi and L. Benkherouf, On an inventory model for deteriorating items with stock dependent and time varying demand rates, *Comp. & Oper. Research*, **31**, (2004), 223- 240.
- [10] K. S. Wu and L.Y. Ouyang and C.T. Yang, An optimal replenishment policy for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with stock dependent demand and partial backlogging, *I.J.P.E.*, **101**, (2006), 369-384.
- [11] L.Y. Ouyang *et al.*, Retailer's ordering policy for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with quantity discount, stock dependent demand and stochastic backorder rate, *J.C.I.I.E.*, 25(1), (2008), 62-72.
- [12] H. Soni and N. H. Shah, Optimal ordering policy for stock-dependent demand under progressive payment scheme, *E.J.O.R.*, **184 (1)**, (2008), 91-100.